

Traditional Hygiene and Healthcare Practices in Assam: A Cultural Tapestry of Wellness

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This paper explores the rich and diverse traditional hygiene and healthcare practices embedded in the cultural heritage of Assam, shedding light on indigenous wisdom that has sustained communities for generations. The study delves into the holistic approach of Assamese communities towards maintaining health and hygiene, encompassing practices rooted in local ecology, cultural beliefs, and traditional healing methods. The research investigates traditional cleanliness rituals, sanitation practices, and dietary habits that contribute to overall well-being in Assam. It explores the use of natural resources such as indigenous herbs, plant extracts, and locally sourced materials for personal hygiene and preventive healthcare along with the cultural significance of rituals and ceremonies associated with health and hygiene. This emphasizes the interconnectedness of physical, mental, and spiritual aspects of well-being. Present study underscores the importance of documenting and preserving these traditional practices as part of Assam's cultural heritage and as potential sources of alternative or complementary healthcare that will contribute to the integration of traditional knowledge into contemporary healthcare strategies.